

PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF GYMNASTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article is about the physical education of students in gymnastics

Gymnastic exercises, along with such natural means of physical development as walking and running, have been known to man for thousands of years. In China and India more than three thousand years ago, gymnastic exercises were performed for therapeutic purposes. Since Peter the Great, gymnastic exercises have been performed in the army in order to strengthen the body and spirit.

Those who served in the Soviet army and Navy perfectly remember how every morning began - the obligatory jogging and gymnastics. Modern armed forces do not depart from these traditions. On the contrary, gymnastics acquires a more athletic shade, a greater bias goes towards strength gymnastics.

And what about the student youth? As such, gymnastics is not included in the programs of higher educational institutions. Such sports as athletics, skiing, volleyball, basketball, swimming are included in the curriculum, but gymnastics is not in the usual form from school. There is no crossbar, no logs, no bars, no support jump, no rope and rings, as there are no acrobatic exercises. Nevertheless, gymnastics is present at every practical lesson. Along with the basic means of physical education listed above, gymnastics is designed to promote health, harden the body, and educate moral and volitional qualities. Like any sports discipline, gymnastics solves three main tasks:

1. Wellness - health promotion; development of individual muscle groups and the entire muscular system, development of correct posture, gait, general development and strengthening of the respiratory system and cardiovascular system, improvement of metabolism and increased vital activity of the body.
2. Educational - to promote comprehensive harmonious physical development: education of strength, flexibility, endurance, dexterity, coordination, expressiveness and

precision of movements. To equip students with the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary in everyday life and in work.

3. Educational: the formation of collectivism, discipline, determination, determination, perseverance, perseverance, endurance, initiative.

Considering that gymnastics as a subject in higher education is not studied, but is an auxiliary discipline, it is used as a warm-up in the preparatory part and in the final part of the lesson it is used when there is a hitch. Consequently, the amount of gymnastics equipment is also small.

Drill exercises are simple motor actions of an official nature, used for more organized classes, rational placement of students during exercises. They are of independent importance when acquiring the skills of rhythmic coordinated actions when walking and running to the score or musical accompaniment, the skills of correct posture.

Various types of walking - walking in a marching step, walking with a high hip lift, on the inner and outer arch of the foot, on toes and heels, walking in a half-squat and in a full squat themselves have a strengthening and developing orientation. An important part of the drill is rebuilding on the spot and in motion. Unfortunately, today's students, for the most part, are not trained in such exercises. But the correct, precise execution of drill commands, quick organized rearrangements save time, develop excellent posture and foster a sense of elbow, a sense of command.

In higher education, this disadvantage must be eliminated. Moreover, the hour and a half allotted for the lesson, with a good load, not all students can do it and you can use drill training as an unloading.

General developmental exercises are widely used in all types of gymnastics. These are simple motor actions in coordination — exercises performed in order to prepare the body, in particular the nervous and muscular systems, for more complex work in the main part of the lesson.

The same exercises, with proper selection, solve the tasks of general physical training, such as the development of various muscle groups, improving physical qualities, and acquiring elementary motor skills.

There are many exercises performed without objects and with various objects and weights, using gymnastic and exercise equipment. Exercises with objects are preferably used in small groups of students. After all, as a rule, the number of objects, whether they are jump ropes, gymnastic sticks, hoops or balls, is limited. The same obstacle applies when using exercise equipment.

Therefore, it remains to use gymnastic exercises more widely without subjects, carefully selecting them to solve the tasks of the lesson. It is necessary to pay more attention to exercises in pairs and using your own weight. Exercises in pairs, as a rule, cause an emotional uplift in students, which is quite important for the general background of classes. In addition, these exercises make you focus on your partner, adapt, and sometimes help him.

Exercises with your own weight are very important and very effective. So, for the development of the muscles of the upper shoulder girdle and back, a universal exercise is used

- flexion and extension of the arms lying down. Its versatility lies in the fact that by simply changing the starting position, namely the width of the arms and legs, we can increase or decrease the load on certain muscle groups and even muscle bundles, when changing the angle of inclination of the trunk during this exercise. For example, arm flexion is performed when the arms and legs are in the same plane, or in different planes when a gymnastic bench is used.

The same applies to the performance of exercises such as "squatting emphasis - lying emphasis", exercises for the abdominal muscles in a sitting or lying position.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the methodological guidelines when performing general developmental exercises. Before performing a new exercise, it is necessary to clearly state the requirements that must be fulfilled in order for the performance of this exercise to give the desired result.

An exercise performed many times with errors develops a certain incorrect stereotype of movement, which is much more difficult to correct, and the difficulty of performing such exercises is not in overcoming external forces, but in the accuracy and clarity of their execution, and this is due to overcoming internal resistance.

Repeated correct repetition of gymnastic exercises helps to overcome internal resistance. In this regard, it is important to notice the error in time and correct it. If the whole group makes mistakes, then it is necessary to repeat the exercise as a whole group, achieving clarity and coherence in completing the task.

In those groups in which more attention was paid to the correctness and clarity of performing drill and general developmental exercises, posture improved significantly, coordination improved, movements were performed easily, accurately, beautifully. It is significant that more than half of the male students, starting from the second year and until graduation, regularly attended the gym. The girls had a slightly different result, they actively began to visit fitness clubs. In any case, they chose a healthy lifestyle.

References

1. Barshay, V. M. Fizicheskoe razvitiye, fizicheskaya podgotovlennost' i rabotosposobnost' uchashchiesya amolodezhi [Tekst] / V. M. Barshay. - Rostov n/D, 1987. - S. 58- 65.
2. Gimnastika / Pod redaksiyey A. T. Brikina. - M., 1971.
3. Petrov P. K. Metodika prepodavaniya gimnastiki v shkole : uchebnyy dlya vuzov / P. K. Petrov. - M.; Vlados. - 2003. - 448 s.